

Research Software and NRENs in Asia

Episode 2: Research Software and Environmental Research in Asia

Session information

Webpage	https://rse-asia.github.io/RSE_Asia/event/2026-3-10_ep-2-open_sharing/
Date	11 March 2026
Time	07:00 - 08:00 am UTC
Facilitators	Saranjeet Kaur Bhogal Jyoti Bhogal
Guest	Dr. Veerachai Tanpipat
Zoom registration	https://us06web.zoom.us/meeting/register/JGnHlnKZSr-vg-e7xMyumg#/registration

Important links

- Registration link - Community Webinar: [Connecting Research Software to the Scholarly Record with DataCite](#)
- [RSE Asia survey link](#)
- RSE Asia [Community Membership form](#)

Resources and info from us

RSE Asia

- Website: https://rse-asia.github.io/RSE_Asia/
- For the latest news, events, activities, and opportunities, follow us on our [LinkedIn page](#)
- To join the RSE Asia community, please fill out our short [Community Membership Form](#)

Shared resources from the session

- Organisations
 - [Asia Pacific Advanced Network](#), Asia
 - [Asia Supercomputer Community \(ASGC\)](#)
 - [Chulalongkorn University](#), Thailand
 - [CODATA](#), France
 - [DataCite](#), Germany
 - [European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts \(ECMWF\)](#), Italy, Germany, and the UK
 - [European Grid Infrastructure \(EGI\)](#), Netherlands
 - [European Space Agency \(ESA\)](#)
 - [Hydroinformatics Institute](#), Thailand
 - [Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency \(JAXA\)](#), Japan
 - [Korea Institute of Science and Technology Information \(KISTI\)](#), South Korea
 - [Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries Research Network \(MAFFIN\)](#), Japan
 - [National Agriculture and Food Research Organization \(NARO\)](#), Japan
 - [National Institute of Informatics \(NII\)](#), Japan
 - [National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration \(NOAA\)](#), USA
 - [National Research and Innovation Agency \(BRIN\)](#), Indonesia
 - [Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical and Astronomical Services Administration \(PAGASA\)](#), Philippines
 - [Philippines Space Agency](#), Philippines
 - [UniNet](#), Thailand
 - [United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific \(UN ESCAP\)](#), Thailand

- [United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction \(UNDRR\)](#), Switzerland
- [UNESCO](#), France
- [United Nations Platform for Space-based Information for Disaster Management and Emergency Response \(UN-SPIDER\)](#), Austria
- APAN working groups
 - [Agriculture Working Group](#)
 - [Disaster Mitigation Working Group](#)
 - [Open Science Collaborative and Resource \(OSCR\)](#)
- Programmes
 - [Copernicus programme](#), European Union
 - [Genomics Beacon Project](#)
- Research Infrastructure/Platform/Services
 - [Global Forecast System \(GFS\)](#)
 - [Google Earth Engine](#)
 - [GSMap rainfall dataset](#)
 - [National Computational Infrastructure \(NCI\)](#)
 - [ThaiREN](#)
 - [Weather Research and Forecasting Model \(WRF\)](#)
 - [Windy application/platform](#)
- Networks/National Research Infrastructure
 - [Philippines Space Agency Data Centre](#)
 - [Hydroinformatics Institute/ThaiWater mobile application](#)
- Concepts / Frameworks
 - [UNESCO AI Ethics framework](#)
 - [Citizen Science](#)
 - [International Disaster Charter](#)
 - [Ensemble Weather Modelling](#)
 - [FAIR Data Principles](#)
 - [Metadata Standards](#)
 - [Open Science](#)
 - [Open Source Software/Open Code Practices](#)

Upcoming events from around the world

- [WUNCA 47](#), 11-13 Feb 2026, Thailand
- [ISGC2026](#), 15-20 March 2026, Taipei, Taiwan
- [APAN62](#), 10-14 August 2026, New Zealand
- [Research Software Asia Australia 2026 Conference](#), 25 - 28 August 2026, online
- [Singapore Open Research Conference](#), 4-5 Nov 2026. All are welcome! Contact person: Su-Nee, GOH, Nanyang Technological University (Singapore) Library. Email: sunee@ntu.edu.sg